

Analyzing Near-Earth Objects for Asteroid Mining

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Abstract. New industry advancements from rocket companies such as SpaceX and Blue Origin are making asteroid mining ever more feasible and a real possibility in the future. Asteroid mining will capitalize on Near Earth Objects (NEOs) as sources for commercially profitable material, such as water and platinum group metals. To be able to profitably mine asteroids, the number of NEOs that are large enough and in range of industry rockets must be found. This research applies two different flight burn paths to calculate the delta-v requirements for a distribution of 802,000 synthetic NEOs. We find there are 198 NEOs with a delta-v requirement less than 5 km/s. Additionally, we calculate mass estimates and characteristic energy values for the synthetic distribution of NEOs. We developed estimates for the number of ore bearing asteroids with absolute magnitude, $17 < H < 25$. We find that PGM ore-bearing asteroids are rare, yet profitable, while water-bearing asteroids are more common. Both types of ore-bearing asteroids are fractions of the overall population however - only 0.3% of asteroids are considered ore-bearing. We estimate that there are 87 PGM ore-bearing asteroids in this population. These NEOs would contain at least \$1 billion in PGMs, and be accessible at a $C3 \leq 12 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$. Further, 22 of the 87 asteroids are primary mining targets. These 22 asteroids contain at least \$10 billion in PGMs and are accessible at a $C3 \leq 10 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$. For asteroid mining for water, we estimate there are 2,460 ore-bearing asteroids in this population, meeting the criteria of an evaluation of \$1 billion in water and a $C3 \leq 12 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$. Further we find that 2,063 of the 2,460 asteroids are primary targets, as they contain a \$10 billion evaluation in water and have a $C3 \leq 10 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$.

1 Introduction

In the past decade, asteroid mining has become a real consideration and a candidate for future investment¹. Defined as the exploitation of raw materials from asteroids, asteroid mining has attracted both the attention of astrophysicists and financial institutions. Scientist Neil DeGrasse Tyson believes the first trillionaire will make their wealth from mining asteroids², and investment firm Goldman Sachs has published to clients that the barriers to asteroid mining are lower than expected³.

¹Glester, Andrew. 'The Asteroid Trillionaires.' Physics World, 11 June 2018, physicsworld.com/a/the-asteroid-trillionaires/.

²Kramer, Katie. 'Neil DeGrasse Tyson Says Space Ventures Will Spawn First Trillionaire.' NBCNews.com, NBCUniversal News Group, 11 June 2015, www.nbcnews.com/science/space/neil-degrasse-tyson-says-space-ventures-will-spawn-first-trillionaire-n352271.

³Glester

Asteroid mining would target ore-bearing asteroids, which hold commercially profitable material. Elvis (2013) notes that there are two groups of commercially profitable material that ore-bearing asteroids may contain: Platinum Group Metals (PGMs) and water. PGMs include ruthenium, rhodium, palladium, osmium, iridium and platinum, and have an estimated market value of \$50 k/kg⁴ due to their rarity on Earth. Elvis (2013) notes that the asteroids richest in PGMs are Ni-Fe asteroids, which are classified as M-type.

For water, a market would have to be developed in space. Water may be used for a variety of reasons in the future, including radiation shielding, life support, and separation into oxygen and hydrogen for rocket fuel. Elvis (2013) estimates a market value of \$5 k/kg for water, as that is roughly the cost of transporting a kg of any material to Low Earth Orbit (LEO). The cost of transporting water from Earth would dictate the market value until water could be successfully mined in greater quantities.

For asteroid mining to become feasible, we need to know the number of asteroids which are accessible, and the number of asteroids which might be profitable. Asteroids which meet these criteria would be defined as ore-bearing and would be of interest for future asteroid mining missions.

1.1 Estimating Ore-bearing Asteroids

Elvis (2013) gave a preliminary number of ore-bearing asteroids by examining NEOs, estimating that there are 10 ore-bearing PGM asteroids, and 18 ore-bearing water asteroids. However Elvis (2013) noted that these preliminary estimates are not only imprecise but also sensitive to small changes, due to limited NEO discovery and understanding. The formulation derived by Elvis (2013) is of great value to us and we begin our research by using said formulation.

The following is the method for assessing the number of ore-bearing asteroids N_{ore} of a given population bigger than a certain mass $N(> M_{\text{min}})$:

$$N_{\text{ore}} = P_{\text{ore}} \times N(> M_{\text{min}})$$

$$P_{\text{ore}} = P_{\text{type}} \times P_{\text{rich}} \times P_{\text{acc}} \times P_{\text{eng}}$$

P_{type} is the probability that an asteroid is of the type that contains ore. P_{rich} is the probability that the type of asteroid is rich in the relevant resource. P_{acc} is the probability that the asteroid is accessible, and P_{eng} is the probability that the resource can be extracted from an engineering standpoint. In Elvis (2013), P_{eng} is assumed to be one because it is too difficult to estimate, and we hold this same assumption in our research. This means our estimates are upper bounds for the number of ore-bearing asteroids.

Much has changed since Elvis (2013) presented the estimate of 10 PGM and 18 water ore-bearing asteroids. Namely, a greater understanding of the number

⁴'MetalDaily.com: Live Gold Prices, Gold Charts and Gold Headlines.' Metals Daily, www.metalsdaily.com/live-prices/pgms/.

of NEOs, as more have been discovered at an exponential rate ⁵. New launchers being developed such as SpaceX’s Falcon Heavy and Blue Origin’s New Glenn will make more NEOs accessible. Both of these updates affect P_{acc} . P_{eng} is still unknown and we assume it equals one in this paper. We use the values for P_{type} and P_{rich} derived in Elvis as they have not changed since 2013.

Taylor, McDowell, Elvis (2018) explored delta-v calculations for the main asteroid belt. There is 10^6 times more mass in the main asteroid belt than in Near Earth Asteroids, making the main belt a primary target for mining. Taylor et al (2018) found that there are 5,211 targets with a delta-v less than 8 km/s but only 7 targets with a delta-v less than 7 km/s. In this paper, we use the methods from Taylor et al (2018) to calculate delta-v requirements to asteroids. This helps us determine the number of asteroids which are accessible, which is an important part of the formulation developed in Elvis (2013).

This research uses the formulation developed by Elvis (2013) and methods from Taylor, McDowell, Elvis (2018), to estimate the number of ore-bearing asteroids in a population model from Granvik et al (2018). A realization of the Granvik et al (2018) model estimates the number of NEOs with an absolute magnitude in the range of $17 < H < 25$. This realization of the Granvik et al (2018) model is a synthetic population of 802,000 NEOs. We use this synthetic population because it provides a statistically accurate representation of the NEO population with H-magnitude $17 < H < 25$. Granvik et al (2018) notes that the population of NEOs with H-magnitude $H < 17$ is relatively well studied, which led to their research of those NEOs with H greater than 17. A statistically accurate model population allows us to perform the calculations we are interested in, even though it is not real data on existing NEOs, which hasn’t been obtained yet. The model provides the semimajor axis, eccentricity, inclination, longitude of ascending node, argument of perihelion, mean anomaly, and absolute magnitude for each synthetic NEO in the model population. We calculate estimates for the number of ore-bearing asteroids with $17 < H < 25$.

⁵<https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?feature=7194>

Fig. 1: Semi-Major Axis vs Eccentricity plot for the Granvik et al (2018) population model

Fig 1 gives a preliminary look at the distribution of the Granvik et al (2018) population model. We see that a majority of asteroids reside at relatively high eccentricities and too great of semi-major axis values to be of interest. When looking for candidates, we want asteroids with low eccentricity and semi-major axis values as they will be more easily accessible. There is a distinct line present, the line of perihelion, which exists due to the definition of NEOs as an asteroid or comet with perihelion of 1.3 astronomical units or less.

2 NEO Masses

2.1 Absolute Magnitude of Minor Planet

The NEO model population from Granvik et al (2018) includes H-magnitude values. H-magnitude is the absolute magnitude of a minor planet, which in our case are asteroids, and is defined as the magnitude the minor planet would have if it were 1 AU from the Earth and 1 AU from the Sun with a phase angle of 0 degrees. Smaller H-magnitudes correspond to brighter objects, which correspond to larger size, for some albedo. H-magnitude provides great value to us as it allows us to calculate estimates for the size of NEOs. This model population from Granvik et al (2018) focuses on NEOs in the range of $17 < H < 25$ because the number of asteroids with an absolute magnitude value less than 17 is well studied, and believed to be around 900, according to Granvi et al (2018). An

absolute magnitude of less than 17 corresponds to those asteroids of size 1 km and greater. However while these larger NEOs have been largely accounted for, estimates for sub 1 km NEOs have generally been lacking until Granvik et al (2018). This model population allows us to examine NEOs in the relatively unstudied range of $17 < H < 25$.

Fig. 2: Histogram of H-Magnitude Values, Granvik et al (2018) population model

We see in fig 2 that a vast majority of the asteroids reside at higher H-magnitude values, which correspond to smaller diameters. We are interested in the lower H-magnitude asteroids as they correlate to larger sizes, which means more possibility for containing large amounts of commercially profitable material.

2.2 Diameter calculations

Since Granvik et al (2018) provides the H-magnitude values for the 802,000 synthetic NEOs in its model population, we can estimate the diameters of these synthetic NEOs. The relation between absolute magnitude and diameter is given by:

$$D = \frac{1329}{\sqrt{p}} \cdot 10^{-0.2H}$$

Where D is diameter, H is absolute magnitude, and p is the geometric albedo of the asteroid. Geometric albedo quantifies how much light the asteroid or planetary body reflects. An asteroid that reflects all light on it would have a value of $p = 1$ and an asteroid that absorbed all light would have a value of $p = 0$. Asteroids typically have a geometric albedo value of $0.05 < p < 0.25$ ⁶, and for

⁶<http://www.physics.sfasu.edu/astro/asteroids/sizemagnitude.html>

our purposes, we used a value of 0.15 for all asteroids, as there currently is no way to accurately predict these values for specific asteroids. With the diameters of the NEOs calculated, we estimated the mass of each NEO in the Granvik et al (2018) population model.

2.3 Mass

We calculate mass estimates for the asteroids in the Granvik et al (2018) population by assuming a spherical shape and a density. We use the previously calculated diameter values to get radii values and use $V = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3$ to estimate the volume of the NEOs in the model population.

For density, we used the results of Carry (2012), which characterized the densities of asteroids according to type. Carry estimated mass and volume for 287 main belt asteroids to calculate their densities and found average density values for each type of asteroid.

We first consider asteroid mining for PGMs. Carry (2012) noted that the average density of M-type asteroids is 4.6 g/cm³. We multiply this density by volume to obtain mass estimates of the model population.

Next, for asteroid mining focused on water, we look to carbonaceous (C-type) asteroids, as they are the most likely source of water, as noted in Elvis (2013). The average density of C-type asteroids is 1.4 grams per cubic centimeter, considerably less than PGMs, as noted in Carry (2012). We multiply this density with the volumes previously calculated to find mass estimates for the water bearing asteroids in the Granvik et al (2018) population model.

2.3.1 Mass Uncertainty

The greatest uncertainty in our research is introduced in our mass calculations of synthetic NEOs. Recalling the equation to get diameter from H-magnitude, we see that values are heavily dependent on albedo inputs:

$$D = \frac{1329}{\sqrt{p}} \cdot 10^{-0.2H}$$

Albedo values may range from 0.05 to .25 and volume is proportional to cubic radii so albedo alone introduces a factor of 11 in uncertainty. For example, two asteroids with assumed densities of 4 g/cm³, one of which has an albedo of .05, and the other with an albedo with .25, would lead to mass estimates of 6.9×10^9 t and 6.2×10^8 respectively.

We also do not have exact density measurements for asteroids. Based off the work from Carry (2012) we can realistically expect density to range from 1 g/cm³ to 4g/cm³. Because we multiply density by our volume estimates, we introduce another factor of 4 in uncertainty through density estimates. Between albedo and density uncertainty, our mass estimates range by a factor of 44.

3 Delta - V

Next we perform delta-V calculations for the Granvik NEO population model. Delta-v measures impulse per unit of mass and is measured in kilometers per second. Knowing the delta-v requirements for the synthetic NEOs in the Granvik NEO population model informs us to the number of asteroids that are within reach of current and future launchers.

We use a method for calculating delta-v requirements developed by Taylor, McDowell, Elvis (2018). We utilize two different flight burn paths, which start from Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and end with a rendezvous with a NEO. This method is applied to the synthetic distribution of the Granvik NEO population model.

Delta-v measures the change in velocity required to reach an asteroid's orbit. We can measure delta-v through the rocket equation:

$$\Delta V = v_e \ln\left(\frac{m_i}{m_f}\right)$$

This equation gives us the relation between ΔV (measured in km/s), v_e , the exhaust velocity of the launcher (in units of km/s), and $\frac{m_i}{m_f}$ which is the ratio of the initial mass to the final mass. We care about measuring the delta-v capabilities of launchers, as well as calculating the delta-v requirements of NEOs. Comparing the two tells us how many NEOs we can actually reach given a launcher's capabilities.

3.1 Two Methods

We use two methods of Taylor et al (2018) to calculate the delta-v values for the NEOs in the Granvik et al (2018) population model. The first method is a three burn maneuver to rendezvous with an object in space from a LEO orbit. The maneuver begins by performing a burn to escape the spacecraft from Earth's gravity and align the apoapsis of the spacecraft above the Sun with the apoapsis of the asteroid. A second burn is performed to change the direction of the spacecraft's velocity such that the spacecraft and the asteroid will rendezvous at the same time. Finally a third burn is performed when the spacecraft is encountering the asteroid at apoapsis to match the velocity of the spacecraft with the velocity of the asteroid.

The second method we use, also developed by Anthony Taylor, is a two burn method. The first burn sends the spacecraft to the apoapsis of the asteroid, and is timed such that the spacecraft and the asteroid would arrive at the same time. A second burn is performed to match the velocities of the spacecraft and asteroid, as done in the three burn method previously discussed.

For both the two and three burn methods, summing the delta-v required for each individual burn gives the delta-v required for the total maneuver. Code developed by Taylor calculates the delta-v required for performing both the two burn and three burn methods, and chooses the more efficient rendezvous meth-

ods. We were able to modify this script and calculated the delta-v requirements for the 802,000 synthetic NEOs in the Granvik et al (2018) model population.

We plot the delta-v values calculated in both a histogram and a cumulative histogram.

Fig. 3: Delta-V Values to go from LEO to a given asteroid in the Granvik et al (2018) population model

Fig. 4: Delta-V cummulative histogram, Granvik et al (2018) population model

Fig. 5: Histogram of 198 asteroids with Delta-V values less than 5 km²/s²

Figures 3 and 4 show that a small fraction of the overall population is accessible via a delta-v less than 5 km²/s². We find there are only 198 asteroids with a Delta-V less than 5 km²/s², as seen in figure 5.

4 Characteristic Energy

4.1

The delta-v achievable for a given payload mass depends on the capability of the rocket used to launch the payload. This capability is quantified by the "characteristic energy" of the launcher. Characteristic energy (C3) is the square of the departure hyperbolic excess speed, measured in km²/s². C3 is the amount of extra energy per unit mass that a rocket has after it escapes the gravity field of a large body. Scientific missions to Mars have required a C3 value of about 10 km²/s², so comparing rockets at this value generally gives us a good idea as to the capabilities of rockets for reaching various NEOs.

Table 1 specifies C3 capabilities at different payloads for various launchers

SpaceX's Falcon Heavy is the most capable launcher for asteroid mining missions ⁸. Official C3 data has not been released by these manufactures yet (except for the Falcon 9), however estimates can be made from the dimensions of the rockets, and how much fuel they may hold.

⁸<https://elvperf.ksc.nasa.gov/Pages/Default.aspx>

C3	Falcon Heavy Payloads	Delta IV Payloads	Atlas V 511 Payloads	Falcon 9 Payloads
10	12 t	9 t	5 t	1.7 t
20	10 t	7 t	4 t	1.25 t
45	5 t	4 t	2 t	0.22 t
80	2 t	1.8 t	N/A	N/A

Table 1: Launcher C3 Capabilities⁷

New Glenn is less suited for such a mission, as preliminary calculations based on the dimensions of the rocket estimate it will carry only 3 tons to $C3 = 10 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$ ⁹.

We can look to a current scientific mission to consider C3 requirements for asteroid mining. The OSIRIS-REx mission, an asteroid sample return project, sent a spacecraft which officially arrived at an asteroid named Bennu, on December 3, 2018¹⁰. The spacecraft is currently surveying the asteroid and will take a sample from Bennu in 2020 to return to Earth.

The OSIRIS-REx spacecraft escaped Earth with a hyperbolic escape speed of 5.41 km/s ¹¹, which corresponds to a C3 value of $29.3 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$. It launched aboard an Atlas V 411, which was able to host a payload of 2 t to the C3 value of $29.3 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$ ¹². The latest configuration of the Atlas V launcher is the 511, which has greater capability, as seen in table 1. OSIRIS-REx is expected to return a sample slightly greater than 60 g back to Earth, a very small fraction of the mass that would needed to be exploited for profitable mining missions. The performance of this mission provides some assurance that the estimates we use for launchers are generally accurate, given these next-generation rockets are predicted to have slightly better performance.

4.2

With these next generation rockets in mind, we calculate how much C3, or excess energy, is required for reaching the NEOs in the Granvik et al (2018) population model.

For the 2 and 3 burn methods, the first burn performed is defined:

$$M1 = V_{\text{peri}} - V_{\text{park}}$$

Where V_{peri} is the geocentric velocity at periapsis and V_{park} is the geocentric velocity at the parked orbit. However we can also use the relation:

$$V_{\text{peri}}^2 = V_{\text{esc}}^2 + C3$$

Where V_{esc}^2 is the escape velocity of Earth. C3 is also defined by the relation:

$$C3 = (V_{\text{TrPeri}} - V_{\text{Earth}})^2$$

⁹<https://www.spacelaunchreport.com/newglenn.html>

¹⁰<https://www.asteroidmission.org/asteroid-operations/>

¹¹<http://spaceflight101.com/osiris-rex/osiris-rex-mission-profile/>

¹²<https://directory.eoportal.org/web/eoportal/satellite-missions/o/osiris-rex>

Where V_{TrPeri} is the heliocentric velocity at transfer periapsis.

So for calculating C3, we simply need the velocity of the Earth and the velocity at transfer periapsis, which are defined as:

$$V_{\text{Earth}} = \sqrt{\frac{M_{\text{sun}} G}{R_{\text{Earth}}}} = 29.78 \text{ km/s}$$

$$V_{\text{TrPeri}} = \sqrt{G \cdot M_{\text{sun}} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{R_{\text{Earth}}} - \frac{2}{R_{\text{node}} + R_{\text{earth}}} \right)}$$

Where R_{Earth} is the heliocentric distance of the Earth and R_{node} is the radius at either the ascending or descending node, whichever is greater. The radius of the ascending node is:

$$R_a = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cos(\omega)}$$

And the radius of the descending node is:

$$R_d = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cos(\pi - \omega)}$$

Since the Granvik et al (2018) model population supplies values for the semi-major axis a , eccentricity e , and argument of periapsis ω , we solve for the ascending and descending nodes, choose the greater of the two, then solve for the transfer periapsis velocity, and then solve for a C3 value. We perform these calculations for the entire Granvik et al (2018) population model.

Fig. 6: C3 values, Granvik et al (2018) population model

As we see in figure 6, very few asteroids actually are accessible at a C3 value less than or equal to 12. The vast majority of asteroids in this population are inaccessible.

Fig. 7: Semi-Major Axis vs Eccentricity Scatter Plot, with H-Magnitude distinctions

Figure 7 shows the relation between Delta-V and C3. There is a large population of asteroids that reside at lower delta-v values but relatively high C3 values.

5 Criteria for Ore-Bearing Asteroids

Once we calculated mass and C3 values for all the synthetic NEOs in the Granvik et al (2018) population, we selected for large accessible NEOs as candidates for ore-bearing asteroids. When considering the specifications for an ore-bearing asteroid, we use the requirements from Elvis (2013), which consist of at least a \$1 billion evaluation, and be accessible by a C3 value of less than or equal to $12 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$. The \$1 billion evaluation is important because most interplanetary missions cost on the order of magnitude of a billion dollars, and asteroid mining will only occur if profit is possible. A C3 value of $\leq 12 \text{ km}^2 / \text{s}^2$ is used as benchmark to determine if the asteroid is accessible or not. Missions to Mars typically have C3 requirements of 10 - 12 km^2/s^2 , as seen by NASA's MAVEN mission which required a C3 of $12 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$ to reach a heliocentric Mars orbit¹³.

¹³<http://spaceflight101.com/maven/mission-profile/>

This serves as our benchmark for accessible asteroids, given mining missions would require larger payloads.

5.1 PGM Ore-Bearing Asteroids

Considering PGM mining first, we define a subset population of those asteroids which have a C3 value less than or equal to 12, and a mass large enough to generate a \$1 billion evaluation. As noted in Elvis (2013), at a density of 4.6 g/cm^3 , an asteroid with a mass of 2.36×10^6 metric tons would conservatively contain 23.6 mt of PGMs. At the market value of \$50K/Kg, the material would be worth \$1.1 Billion. Therefore, for PGM ore-bearing asteroids, we choose a mass greater than 2.36×10^6 metric tons, as Elvis (2013) estimated, to determine if contains enough material.

For the 802,000 synthetic NEOs in the Granvik et al (2018) population model, we calculate C3 values and mass estimates to find that there are 4,346 targets which meet the preliminary criteria of $C3 \leq 12$ and $M \geq 2.36 \times 10^6 \text{ mt}$.

Using the formulation developed in Elvis (2013), we multiply the number of high mass, low C3 NEOs with the probability that the asteroid is of the correct type to be rich in commercially profitable material, $p_{\text{type}} = 0.04$, and the probability that the asteroid actually contains a substantial amount of that material, $p_{\text{rich}} = 0.5$, to conclude that there are $4346 \times .04 \times .5 \approx 87$. ore-bearing asteroids.

We also define a subset population of target asteroids which would meet a criteria of being worth \$10 billion. We simply increase the mass requirement to 2.36×10^7 metric tons, and increase the C3 requirement to 10 to note the asteroids of priority, as they have an order of magnitude greater evaluation, and are even more accessible due to the lower C3 value. Under these more specific parameters, we find that there are 1,109 priority targets. Once again, we apply $p_{\text{rich}} = 0.5$ and $p_{\text{type}} = 0.04$ to find there are approximately 22 priority targets for PGMs.

5.2 Water Ore-Bearing Asteroids

Next, we consider mining asteroids for water. As previously discussed, selling water in LEO is estimated to have a market value of \$5K / Kg. Based off this value, Elvis estimates that only an 18 m diameter asteroid is needed to obtain \$1 billion in water because resource extraction is 20,000 times higher for water than for PGMs. For every kg of raw asteroid, 20,000 times more mass is extracted in water than in PGMs. Elvis estimates that water ore-bearing asteroids are 20 percent water while PGM ore bearing asteroids are only 10 parts per million, or 0.001 percent, PGM. An 18 m diameter corresponds to a mass of 119 metric tons, using the average density of c-type asteroids, 1.4 grams per centimeter cubed. Therefore, we can select asteroids from the model population that meet the requirements of 119 metric tons and a $C3 = 12$. We find there are 79,375 targets that meet these conditions. Similarly to calculating the number of ore-bearing for PGMs, we apply the corresponding probability that the asteroid is

C3 (km ² /s ²)	Number of Accessible Asteroids	Total Mass of Accessible Asteroids (t)	Number of Ore-Bearing Asteroids	Mass of Ore	Value of Ore
10	6,566	1.2×10 ¹¹	203	2.5×10 ¹⁰	\$1.2×10 ¹⁷
20	141,626	2.5×10 ¹¹	4,390	5.0×10 ¹⁰	\$2.5×10 ¹⁷
45	394,465	7.1×10 ¹¹	12,228	1.4×10 ¹¹	\$7.1×10 ¹⁷
80	766,861	1.5×10 ¹²	23,772	3.0×10 ¹¹	\$1.5×10 ¹⁸

Table 2: Water ore-bearing asteroids: Number of ore-bearing asteroids, the mass of ore and evaluation of that ore are presented

C3 (km ² /s ²)	Number of Accessible Asteroids	Total Mass of Accessible Asteroids (t)	Number of Ore-Bearing Asteroids	Mass of Ore	Value of Ore
10	6,566	4.2×10 ¹¹	131	4.3×10 ⁶	\$2.1×10 ¹⁴
20	141,626	8.3×10 ¹¹	2,832	8.3×10 ⁶	\$4.1×10 ¹⁴
45	394,465	2.3×10 ¹²	7,889	2.3×10 ⁷	\$1.1×10 ¹⁵
80	766,861	4.9×10 ¹²	15,337	4.9×10 ⁷	\$2.5×10 ¹⁵

Table 3: PGM ore-bearing asteroids: Number of ore-bearing asteroids, the mass of ore and evaluation of that ore are presented

the correct type, and the probability that it is rich in the material. For water, we have $p_{\text{rich}} = 0.31$ and $p_{\text{type}} = 0.1$. Multiplying these with the number of high mass, low C3 targets, we find there are 2,460 targets for mining water.

We can also further define a subset of primary target asteroids by selecting for mass that would lead to a \$10 billion evaluation. Constraining the targets to those that meet 1.19×10^3 tons and a $C3 = 10 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$, we find there are 66,563 candidates. Multiplying by p_{type} and p_{rich} gives us 2,063 priority ore-bearing asteroids.

It is important to remember the mass estimates for these calculations contain up to a factor of 44 in uncertainty. Our estimates for the numbers of PGM and water ore-bearing asteroids are subject to this uncertainty as mass estimates determine whether an asteroid is considered ore-bearing. Furthermore, there is uncertainty in the probabilities p_{type} and p_{rich} , which we reference from Elvis (2013). While we are unable to find the extent of these uncertainties, the number we find of ore-bearing asteroids is subject to change greatly based on these probabilities.

6 Discussion Conclusions

We have developed estimates for the number of ore bearing asteroids with absolute magnitude, $17 < H < 25$. While the population of NEOs with $H < 17$ has been relatively well researched, the population of smaller NEOs is less understood. We find that PGM ore-bearing asteroids are rare, yet profitable, while water-bearing asteroids are more common. Both types of ore-bearing asteroids are fractions of the overall population however - only 0.3% of asteroids are considered ore-bearing. We estimate that there are 87 PGM ore-bearing asteroids in this population. These NEOs would contain at least \$1 billion in PGMs, and be accessible at a $C3 \leq 12$. Further, 22 of the 87 asteroids are primary mining targets. These 22 asteroids contain at least \$10 billion in PGMs and are accessible at a $C3 \leq 10$. For asteroid mining for water, we estimate there are 2,460 ore-bearing asteroids in this population, meeting the criteria of an evaluation

of \$1 billion in water and a $C3 \leq 12$. Further we find that 2,063 of the 2,460 asteroids are primary targets, as they contain \$10 billion in water and have a $C3 \leq 10$.

We utilized methods developed by Taylor, McDowell, Elvis (2018) to calculate the delta-v requirements of the synthetic NEOs in the Granvik et al (2018) population. From these delta-v calculations, we are able to derive C3 calculations, and compare the C3 requirements of the asteroids in the model population to C3 capabilities of past and future industry rockets. We focus primarily on SpaceX’s Falcon Heavy because of its ability to carry a payload of 12 tons to a C3 value of 10.

We derive the masses of the Granvik+2018 model population through utilizing the H-magnitude values to estimate diameter of the NEOs, and then estimate a density to finally calculate mass.

Further research is needed as more NEOs are found and industry continues to advance rocket technology. The discovery of NEOs has seen exponential growth since the late 1990’s¹⁴.

Fig. 8: Exponential Discovery of NEOs, particularly those smaller in size

While the number of larger NEOs (H magnitude less than 15) is well researched¹⁵ and believed to be around 900 to 1000, the number of NEOs with an H magnitude greater than 17 is relatively unknown. There are currently approximately 20,000 NEOs known total¹⁶. The model population from Granvik et al (2018) starts to shed light on these smaller NEOs by providing a statistically

¹⁴<https://cneos.jpl.nasa.gov/stats/totals.html>

¹⁵Granvik et al (2018)

¹⁶Home Page. NEOCam, neocam.ipac.caltech.edu/

accurate population to perform analysis on. However further research and discovery needs to occur to further understand these smaller asteroids which could provide a good source of ore-bearing asteroids.

Additionally, more research into the engineering constraints of asteroid mining need to be considered. In our calculations, we assume that $p_{\text{eng}} = 1$, which limits our estimates to an upper bound on the number of ore-bearing asteroids in the $17 < H < 25$ range. A more realistic number needs to be developed as the engineering constraints of asteroid mining are developed.

Our mass estimates were largely impacted by uncertainties, up to a factor of 44. Albedo uncertainties account for a factor of 11, and future mission look to shed light on this uncertainty. The Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) is to soon become operational and will expand the known number of small bodies in our solar system by 1-2 orders of magnitude¹⁷. A more accurate understanding of the number of NEOs will surely enable a more accurate estimate of the number of ore-bearing asteroids. Another project, NEOCam, is a mission that will serve to identify potentially hazardous asteroids near Earth, as well as find the most suitable NEOs for future exploration missions¹⁸. NEOCam will use an infrared telescope to obtain more accurate albedo values to drive more accurate diameter measurements. This would lead to a great reduction in the uncertainty of the figures we present. Together, the LSST and NEOCam will provide greater context on NEO populations and characteristics, and will allow for more certain results.

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